

D4.1 Toolkit Design and System Requirements

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Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

biorural.eu

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Executive Summary

This document presents the design and specifications of the BioRural Toolkit, which will be the main tool developed by BioRural, presenting all the project results. The Toolkit aims to provide access to the results and facilitate the use of information/knowledge collected and generated in the course of the project. It is also meant to enable interaction between rural actors, providing the platform to communicate, exchange experience and knowledge, and seek collaborations in the chosen fields of bioeconomy, thus supporting the wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

This document presents the technical description of the digital tool and the structure designed to provide access to its contents in an intuitive and user-friendly way, discusses the functionalities available to the registered and non-registered users, and proposes different methods for presentation of the content using suitable file formats for specific types of collected material.

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1 BioRural Toolkit Design and Specifications

The Toolkit will follow an open-access user-centered design approach aiming to make available a one-stop web based tool featuring:

- (i) factsheets of the rural Bioeconomy's current status at national, regional and EU level;
- (ii) an inventory of selected research results (papers and projects), commercial bio-based solutions and funding opportunities;
- (iii) an interactive map of the identified ERBN members;
- (iv) the success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material;
- (v) knowledge sharing workshops' recordings and lecture material;
- (vi) outcomes of capacity building workshops in the form of factsheets and audio-visual content;
- (vii) practice abstracts;
- (viii) rural development blueprints;
- (ix) policy and research guidelines.

Each of the above categories will constitute a separate tile in the structure of the BioRural Toolkit as presented in Figure 1.

The Toolkit will be available at: <https://platform.biorural.eu/>

According to the project assumptions, the BioRural Toolkit is meant to be an open stakeholder toolkit, with the aim to provide access to knowledge to as many stakeholders as possible – therefore, it will provide access to its contents without the necessity to register on the website. However, registration will offer additional functionalities to the users, such as e.g. the possibility to download the materials or save them on their personal profiles as well as upload certain types of content.

1.1 Technical description of BioRural Toolkit

BioRural Toolkit is a Wordpress-based web application using various plugins. It depends on Wordpress version 6.1.1 with PHP version 7.4.33. PHP (Personal Hypertext Processor) is a web backend language created to work with HTML code “out of the box” and allow creating web apps without the need to create Front-End and Back-End separately. Version 7.4 is actually the most popular and secure in web development; PHP is connected with the MySQL relational database based on MariaDB engine. The app is working on Linux server using Apache web server as EnviroSolutions company subpage <https://envirosolutions.pl/biorural/>; there are three main directories: wp-admin, wp-content and wp-includes. The first, wp-admin directory, is a general Wordpress directory where are files responsible for the admin page we are working on. The second, wp-content directory is the space for plugins, images, themes and content used to create a page. The third one, the wp-includes directory, includes files responsible for connecting with the database and saving changes.

The main theme of the page is Moon by Osetin by Tamik Sozиеv, however, some parts of the pages are plugin based. The most important plugins we are using to create pages are:

Elementor & Elementor Pro – plugins that allow us to easily edit the page, create forms and other elements,

Youzify – plugin that allows creating a user account and other elements for users' community,

BuddyPress – plugin connected with Youzify and required when we want to create a page,

WP Go Maps – plugin allowing for including a map on the page.

The rest of plugins installed on the page are helpers that add the rest of the required page elements like cookie bar, for example, CookieYes. However, in many cases plugins are insufficient, therefore we need to change some files

and create new scripts to add new opportunities. We code using HTML, CSS, PHP and JavaScript, we prepare code to easily move the website to another server.

As part of the work on planning the tool, the assumptions of the project and all its elements were analysed and the first plan was created.

1.2 Proposed BioRural Toolkit Structure

The structure of BioRural Toolkit has been designed to fulfill the main purpose of this online tool – to provide access to the material collected in the course of the BioRural project implementation, through a user-friendly, intuitive interface, and to facilitate contact and collaboration of its users within the created networks.

The homepage of the BioRural Toolkit will, therefore, consist of an interactive map showing the location of all the registered users, and the categories presenting the collected and generated material on bio-based solutions in an organized way (Figure 1). This layout corresponds to the main principle of the tool – to provide and facilitate the exchange of knowledge.

Figure 1. Proposed BioRural Toolkit Structure

The proposed layout presents the categories listed in chapter 1 clearly and explicitly; each category can be entered by clicking on the specific tile, which will direct the user to a separate page presenting the chosen content. The format of files included within each category and the method of presentation of its contents will be adjusted to the specificity of the material. The file formats will include: Portable Document Format (PDF), Video file formats (MP4), text-based document formats (.doc, .docx, .xls, .ppt, .pptx), graphics (.jpg, .png), and other that may appear suitable in the course of data collection and preparation. All the above file formats have been chosen due to their widely accepted standards and widespread use among Internet users.

1.2.1 Factsheets

The BioRural factsheets aim to provide detailed information on specific bioeconomy topics and their status in a quick and easily digestible way for all stakeholders. For the creation of factsheets, input is initially drawn and populated from the results of T1.1 Current Bioeconomy Status in Europe (M1-M6) [Leader: CERTH; Partners: All].

For ease of access, it was decided to divide the tile into three tabs: EU factsheets, National Factsheets, and Regional factsheets which will present area-specific content in the form of factsheets (PDF) available for download. The Regional Factsheets will be further divided into four categories following the four geographical regions of Europe: SE, SW, NE, and NW. The National Factsheets will consist of reports on bioeconomy status in all 14 project partner countries.

The Factsheets will be prepared following a unified methodology and data presentation to facilitate the interpretation, analysis and comparison of the collected information.

Registered users will also have the option to, after a review process, upload their own bioeconomy factsheets to the platform.

Figure 2. The three tabs present categorization of Factsheets (description under the pictures unclear)

1.2.2 Rural Bioeconomy inventories

The BioRural inventory aims to provide stakeholders with an easily searchable database/repository of rural bioeconomy research results (papers and projects), commercial bio-based solutions and funding opportunities. In the toolkit, the Inventory has been divided into four main categories >Research Papers, Research projects, Commercial biobased solutions and Funding opportunities.

Figure 3. Bioeconomy inventories

The main input for this category will be provided from T4.2: BioRural Toolkit Development, Updates and Maintenance (M4-M36) [Leader: IUNG; Partners: All]. The specific input required from each project partner is provided in Table 1.

Partners	Scientific Papers	Research project	Commercial biobased solutions	Funding oportunities	Total
CERTH	164	1	5	0	170
DELPHY	2	1	5	3	11
VALORIAL	2	1	5	3	11
NATUREPLASTSAS	2	1	5	3	11
IZES	2	1	5	3	11
AU	2	1	5	3	11
IUNG-PIB	2	32	10	0	44
Vytauto	2	1	5	3	11
LLU	2	1	5	3	11
AVEBIOM	2	1	5	3	11
UC	2	1	5	3	11
CBE	2	1	5	3	11
AIEL	2	1	5	3	11
FSH	2	1	5	3	11
ICO	2	1	5	3	11
UL	2	1	5	3	11
ALGEN	2	1	5	3	11
GEA	2	1	5	3	11
GPP	2	1	5	3	11
Total	200	50	100	51	401

Table 1. Input required from each project partner regarding the number of identified relevant bio-based solutions to be fed into the inventory

The specific categories will consist of at least: 200 scientific papers, 50 research projects, 100 commercial bio-based solutions and 50 financing tools collected by the project partners and identified as relevant for the implementation of circular bio-based solutions in rural areas. Each of the collected items will be described using the information provided in the entry form, which will be adjusted to the specificity of a given category and, at the same time, allow for presenting all the solutions in a unified manner, e.g. containing visual materials, short description, contact information etc. Each solution will be assigned to specific bioeconomy sector/sectors and each will be provided with a set of keywords, which will facilitate the search for a desirable solution in the inventories.

The submission form for each of the four categories of solutions will include the questions presented in Table 2.

	scientific papers	research projects	commercial solutions	financing tools
What is the...?	... title of the paper?	... title of the project?	... name of the solution?	... name of the financing tool?
What is the acronym?		x		
What is the native language?	x	x	x	x
What is the abstract/short description?	x	x	x	x
What is the funding source?		x	x	X
What is the budget?		x	... price?	X
What is the name of...?	...the author?	...the coordinator?	...the company?	...the financing institution?
Official website	x	x	x	x
Contact information	x	x	x	x
What is the...	... date of publication?	... project duration?		... financing period?
Specific information (e.g. ...)	aim/subject/results	aim/subject/results	specification	conditions for financing
Provide keywords	x	x	x	x
Choose relevant bioeconomy sector	x	x	x	x
Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)	DOI/link to the repository	x	x	x
Provide additional materials	pdf of the paper	deliverables, brochures	specifications, manuals, instructions	application forms, guides

Table 2. Questions included in the submission forms based on the type of solution

The items collected in each category will be presented as shown in Figure 4, each tile consisting of a picture, title and a short description – the first few sentences of the paper/project abstract or of the short description in the case of a commercial solution/financing tool. The search engine will allow for searching through the collected items based on the keywords/bioeconomy themes/etc.

Figure 4. Collection of bio-based solutions within each of the categories: scientific papers, research projects, commercial solutions, and financing tools

When choosing one of the displayed solutions, the user will be presented with a page containing the information introduced in the designated submission form (see Table 1). The choice of information necessary to be provided for each of the categories of bio-based solutions was determined in a way as to allow for a uniform presentation of all items, regardless of their category. The universal layout for bio-based solutions’ factsheets is presented in Figure 5.

ACTA BIOLOGICA

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Ut elit tellus, luctus nec ullamcorper mattis, pulvinar dapibus leo.

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing Lorem Ipsum passages, and more recently with desktop publishing software like Aldus PageMaker including versions of Lorem Ipsum. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing Lorem Ipsum passages, and more recently with desktop publishing software like Aldus PageMaker including versions of Lorem Ipsum.

INFORMATION

KEYWORDS

plants, clothes, nature

BIOECONOMY THEME

food & agriculture, biomaterials

PROVIDER/SOURCE

NAME OF THE AUTHOR	JOURNAL	
private	Publications	
OFFICIAL WEBSITE/DOI	CONTACT INFORMATION	DATE OF PUBLICATIONS
https://www.mdpi.com/2304-6775/10/1/5	Madrid, Spain	5th May 2022

MATERIAL

AUDIO-VISUAL MATERIALS	ADDITIONAL MATERIALS
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zr65v6HTV38c	https://typeset.io/resources/top-10-journals-by-nature-and-their-templates/
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zr65v6HTV38c	

Figure 5. Factsheet presenting one of the bio-based solutions in the rural bioeconomy inventory

1.2.3 BioRural Success stories

The input for this category will be provided by T2.4 Identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform (M10-M36) [Leader: ICO; Partners: All].

The BioRural success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material will be presented in the toolkit. The aim of these is to provide an easily accessible overview of each success story, showcasing their innovations and factors that drove their development. The success stories are divided along the five bioeconomy themes: Food & agriculture, Forestry & natural habitat, Aquatic & water systems, Bioenergy, and Biomaterials (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Tiles presenting the five themes of bioeconomy

At the launch of the toolkit, the 8 success stories that are included in BioRural and analysed in work package 2 will be available to all stakeholders. These consist of:

- Staramaki (Food & agriculture)
- Bio-based garden (Food & agriculture)
- SCIVEN (Forestry and natural habitats)
- Latvia's State Forests (Forestry and natural habitats)
- PUSTELNIA (Aquatic and water systems)
- ALGEN (Aquatic and water systems)
- ACEITES GUADALENTIN and BIOLIZA (Bioenergy)
- NaturePlast (Biomaterials)

Each of the success stories will have a static page with the main information regarding the presented case, a short description, and a video (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Example of a static page presenting a success story of the Polish Fish Farm “Pustelnia”

Additional success stories will be added to the toolkit as the project progresses. These will come from the identification of success stories in Task 2.4. At the end of the project timeline, each theme will include at least 4 success stories. The audio-visual material produced by BioRural is limited to the 8 original success stories, however, if the newly identified projects/initiatives already have relevant audio-visual material, they will be included as well.

1.2.4 Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials

(previously called: Workshop recordings)

Work package 3 (T.3.1 Online knowledge exchange on Bioeconomy (M1-M36) [Leader: UL; Partners: CERTH, AU, AlgEn, GGP, UC, IUNG, LLU, NP]) will provide input for the inventory of the Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials. A series of five EU online workshops with different groups of stakeholders and devoted to different bioeconomy themes will be organized and recorded to share and disseminate knowledge on bio-based solutions. Each workshop will be held over the course of 3 days covering lectures/discussions on ‘basic concept(s), technical principles,’ ‘showcase of good practices, factors of success’ and ‘cross-cutting themes.’ On each day, 5-6 lectures/discussions of around 15 minutes will be conducted. They will be recorded and the recordings, along with additional educational material, will be available to users categorized according to the bioeconomy themes (Figure 8):

- >Food & agriculture
- >Forestry and natural habitats
- >Aquatic and water systems
- >Bioenergy
- >Biomaterials

Figure 8. Online tutorials repository – videos will be divided into five categories corresponding to the themes of bioeconomy

1.2.5 Interactive Network Map

The aim of the interactive network map is to provide an online space for bioeconomy stakeholders to register and be visible to facilitate cooperation and collaboration between rural bioeconomy stakeholders. Rural bioeconomy stakeholders identified in all tasks and work packages, in particular those identified in Task 2.1, will be invited to register on the toolkit and have the option to be visible on the interactive map. At least 400 stakeholders will be registered to the toolkit by the end of the project. The Interactive Network Map providing information about the registered stakeholders (Figure 9) will be available to access from the homepage. Registered users/all users (TBD) will be able to search for a specific name/organization using the search engine (marked at the top of the map) or filter the stakeholders by type or bioeconomy theme (filtering options available below the map). The types declared by each registered stakeholder will be also visually differentiated using different pin colours for marking the location of stakeholders on the map.

The filtering/search results will be available for download as .xls file (download button in the bottom right corner). They will include the name and type of the stakeholder, bioeconomy theme, name and address of the institution and website address, if provided by the stakeholder.

Figure 9. Interactive map with its functionalities

The choice of stakeholder types will comprise:

- Associations, clusters, NGOs
- Government and public administrations
- Private company/self-employed
- Research and education
- Other

The bioeconomy themes will consist of:

- Aquatic/water systems
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials
- Food/agriculture
- Forestry/natural habitats

Apart from the basic personal information a stakeholder will be required to provide in order to create an account (name, address, stakeholder type, bioeconomy theme), they will also have a possibility of adding a short description

of their activities, organization, work focus etc. and providing contact information including a phone number and website address. The optional contact information consists also of network profiles (Figure 10), which may facilitate creating collaboration networks, finding suitable partners for joint ventures or simply keeping up to date with the activities of other stakeholders in our area of interest.

Figure 10. Profile settings allowing for introduction of additional information such as social networks' profiles

Both the interactive map and the toolkit will be accessible to non-registered users of the website. However, registration will provide additional functionalities, such as storing files on a private account or adding files to the inventory (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Additional functionalities for registered users

Each registered user will be able to add items to the BioRural inventory using a designated online form. The suitable form containing questions relevant for the particular category of bio-based solution will appear upon selecting the category in the search tool, e.g. the form for submitting information on a scientific paper to the inventory will be structured as in Figure 12-14.

The screenshot shows a web interface with a blue header bar containing 'Search by: Inventories'. Below the header, there are three tabs: 'INFORMATION' (selected), 'PROVIDER/SOURCE', and 'MATERIAL'. The 'INFORMATION' section includes a 'Gallery of Pictures' field with a 'Przełóż...' button and the text 'Nie wybrano plików.'. Below this are three text input fields: 'Title of the paper *', 'Short Description *', and 'Provide keywords *'. At the bottom of the section is a 'Bioeconomy theme' section with five radio button options: 'food & agriculture', 'forestry & natural habitat', 'aquatic & water systems', 'bioenergy', and 'biomaterials'. A 'NEXT' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 12. Submission form for scientific papers – information section

The screenshot shows the 'PROVIDER/SOURCE' section of the submission form. It features three tabs: 'INFORMATION', 'PROVIDER/SOURCE' (selected), and 'MATERIAL'. The section contains five text input fields: 'What is the name of the author *', 'Journal *', 'Official website/DOI *', 'Contact information', and 'What is the date of publication *'. At the bottom right, there are two buttons: 'PREVIOUS' and 'NEXT'.

Figure 13. Submission form for scientific papers – provider/source section

INFORMATION	PROVIDER/SOURCE	MATERIAL
Provide audio-visual materials (image, video)		
<input type="text" value="links only"/>		
Provide additional materials (only open source)		
<input type="button" value="Przełóżaj..."/> Nie wybrano plików.		
		<input type="button" value="SEND"/>
		<input type="button" value="PREVIOUS"/>

Figure 14. Submission form for scientific papers – material section

1.2.6 Capacity building workshops

This section aims to synthesize and provide key bioeconomy educational material originating out of the BioRural’s 42 national capacity building workshops. The input for this category will be provided by T3.2 Generation of interactive and multi-actor innovation at national level (M7-M24) [Leader; CERTH, Partners: All]. The tutorials will be divided into three thematic categories: (i) inland raw material production, (ii) aquatic raw material production and (iii) biological raw material processing. Each country will organise three workshops devoted to the above topics. The materials produced for the workshop participants as well as summary reports presenting the most valuable results, insights etc. in the form of factsheets or presentations (PDF) will be available for the registered/all users of the Toolkit (TBD).

Figure 15. Page presenting capacity-building workshops

1.2.7 Practice abstracts

The inventory of practice abstracts will be fed with materials prepared by the project partners and divided into the five categories of bioeconomy themes. All the practice abstracts will be prepared in line with the EIP-AGRI common format. The inventory of practice abstracts is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Inventory of practice abstracts divided into categories corresponding to five bioeconomy themes

1.2.8 Business Blueprints

The inventory of Blueprints will offer business blueprints for rural development in each bioeconomy theme. The blueprints will be divided into categories according to bioeconomy themes, as presented in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Inventory of Business blueprints divided in to categories corresponding to five bioeconomy themes

The Policy and Research guidelines will be presented as drafted in Figure 18. The content for this page will be provided by T3.4 Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development in M24-M36 [Leader: CERTH; Partners: All], therefore, the form of material presentation will be discussed and adjusted to the content produced. The policy guidelines will cover the following areas:

- Interactive and multi-actor innovation processes specific to bio-based solutions for rural areas;
- New funding formats enhancing innovation-driven research about bio-based solutions;
- Future research;
- Topics of interest for the national and EU research agendas (including further HE programming);
- Fostering a better targeted and shared research agenda on innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects.

Figure 18. Page layout for presenting the Policy and research guidelines

1.3 Plan for platform development

The plan for BioRural platform development takes into account the timeline of other work packages, which are to provide the content for the BioRural inventories. The plan assumes that the BioRural Toolkit will be launched operational for its users on **15.05.2023**, however, it will not offer all the above-mentioned functionalities at once. The remaining inventories and functionalities will be incorporated into the existing online tool in the course of the project, as well as the already existing inventories will be continuously updated with the material collected and generated in the other ongoing work packages.

Figure 19. BioRural toolkit development timeline

The toolkit is planned to be showcased during the workshops (T3.2, T3.3) and its functionalities are to be subject for evaluation of Bioeconomy actors, which will allow for an improvement of the tool and development of additional features if necessary.

The BioRural Toolkit will be linked to the existing online bioeconomy tools, such as the [Bioeconomy Platform](#), [AgEnergy Platform](#), and other online tools identified as relevant in this regard.

The BioRural Toolkit will remain operational as an open-access tool for at least three years after the end of the project.

2 Conclusions

BioRural Toolkit is ready to be an online repository of bio-based solutions that enables the interaction between rural actors and provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas allowing the transitions of rural areas from a linear economy to a circular bio-based economy.

The BioRural toolkit will enable networking of stakeholders, knowledge sharing of bioeconomy as well as business models, and will support post-project sustainability. This document presents the technical description of the digital tool and the structure designed to provide access to its contents in an intuitive and user-friendly way, discusses the functionalities available to the registered and non-registered users, and proposes different methods for presentation of the content using suitable file formats for specific types of collected material.

Figure 20. Screenshot of BioRural toolkit homepage